

December 31, 2019

Assessment of *Acacia ampliceps* Maslin aerial Parts for Phytochemical and Antimicrobial Activities

Author's Details:

Fozia Shaheen¹, Muhammad Saleem Khan¹, Faran Durrani², Saad Ullah Khan², Sami Ullah Khan³, Ihsan Ullah²¹Department of Botany, Islamia University Peshawar ²Department of Botany, University of Science and Technology Bannu ³Department of Biotechnology, University of Science and Technology Bannu

Received Date: 08-Dec-2019

Accepted Date: 26-Dec-2019

Published Date: 31-Dec-2019

Abstract

Hundreds of natural compounds are produced by plants that are used in defense against countless diseases, managing insects, fungi and herbivores. Many phytochemicals with possible biological activity have been recognized. Though, as one plant contains extensively diverse phytochemicals, the use of one plant as a whole is uncertain. The current investigations were made to screen *Acacia ampliceps* Maslin for its phytochemical and antimicrobial potential. Results proved the detection of natural products as alkaloids, tannins, reducing sugars, saponins, flavonoids, terpenoids and anthraquinones. Furthermore, we examined the antibacterial activity of the four different solvent extract samples (ethyl acetate, ethanol, chloroform and methanol) against a panel of microorganisms (*Bacillus subtilis*, *Xanthomonas*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli* and *Citrobacter*). Disc-diffusion assay was used with concentrations of 1mg and 2mg/disc. The samples with ethanol extract showed the highest zone of inhibition against *Xanthomonas* (173%) to be the best one. The ethyl acetate extracted sample also showed max. Zone of inhibition against *Xanthomonas* (158%). No inhibition (0%) was found in chloroform extracted samples against all bacterial strains. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was most resistant but *Xanthomonas* specie was most susceptible. It was concluded that the extracts have the potential for isolation of phytochemical and antimicrobial compounds for the pharmaceutical industry. The above results exposed that *Acacia ampliceps* have tremendous antibacterial activity and can be used for disease treatment.

Key words: *Acacia ampliceps* Maslin, phytochemical, antibacterial activities.

INTRODUCTION

Medicinal plants are a significant source of producing phytochemicals, which are used to treat a lot of diseases. The plants contain different chemical compounds that contain curative values. These compounds are called chemical constituents that create a specific physiological effect (Shah *et al.*, 2012; Uddin *et al.*, 2011). The world has viewed rising technical and profitable advantage in medicinal plants and their yield (Ali and Jahangir, 2001). Herbal extracts and new different methods of remedial treatments are eminent these days (Cowan, 1999). Different groups of secondary metabolites have been used in the making of modern medicine or the discovery of new drugs (Uddin *et al.*, 2011). About more than sixty percent of all the pharmaceuticals are plant based (Sanjay *et al.*, 2007). Products of natural origin are obtained from various medicinal plants to cure ailments (Srinivasan *et al.*, 2006; Liu *et al.*, 2011; Oumzil *et al.*, 2002). Consequently, therapeutic plants are ever more helpful in substituting chemical and artificial medicine (Heber, 2004).

Current investigation encourages scientists to screen plants and their extracts in order to disclose the unknown treasury of biological activities (Efferth *et al.*, 2007). In the field of pharmaceuticals, various novel natural and synthetic drugs have been discovered (Preethi *et al.*, 2010). One third of microbial diseases have been treated with synthetic drugs (Sharma, 2011). One way to resolve the conflict with antibiotics is to target the inhibitors obtained from medicinal plants (Kim *et al.*, 1995). Plant based different extracts can target sites apart from antibiotics and are dynamic against pathogens that are resistant to the drug (Ahmad and Beg, 2001). Therefore, scientists are demanding to extract safe plant derived ingredients with sufficient medicinal files for the

December 31, 2019

production of new drugs (Pavithra *et al.*, 2010; Zgoda and Porter, 2001). A complete pharmacological study can be carried out using bioassay outcomes (Saupe, 2005, Doughari, 2006).

In Pakistan, nearly 6000 flowering species of plants are present, out of which almost 700 are medicinally used (Shinwari *et al.*, 2006). The conventional method treatment in Pakistan is almost 75%, which is permitted by prominent herbal experts (Gill, 2003).

The naturally active compounds found in plants are dependable for their therapeutic value and to produce clear effects on human's alkaloids, terpenoids, flavonoids and phenolic compounds (Edeoga *et al.*, 2005). The phytochemical evaluation of *Conyza bonarensis* L. shows the presence of tannins, flavonoids, glycosides, steroids, diterpenoids and saponins. The crude extract of *Conyza bonarensis* exhibited the presence of tannin, flavonoids, saponin and glycosides (Shah *et al.* 2013).

Biological activities of numerous plants are investigated to have secondary metabolites to fight pathogens causing diseases (Sen and Batra, 2012). Flavonoids are substances created by plants against microbial infection and are too much active against a large number of microorganisms (Mandal *et al.*, 2013). Extract from leaves of *Justicia adhatoda* comprises an astonishing suppressing effect against various bacteria like *S. pyogenes*, *K. pneumonia* and *E.coli* (Pa and Mathew, 2012). Chloroform and extracts obtained from ethylacetate of these plants observed uncertain inhibitory effect against bacteria (Rauf *et al.*, 2012). Biological activity of various ethanolic, methanolic, chloroform, aqueous and diethyl ether extracts was tested against *E.coli*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Salmonella*, *etc.*, all the extracts exhibited maximum antibacterial activity (Shinwari *et al.* 2009). The study of extracts and their products for antibacterial activity has discovered that higher plants present a significant cause of novel anti-microbial agents (De Smith, 1997; Cowan, 1999).

Plants are excellent sources to produce metabolites that supply defense in opposition to a variety of pathogens (Ahmad and Beg, 2001). The secondary metabolites of the plant have enormous potential antibacterial compounds particularly in the treatment of pathogenic diseases (Nasir and Chanda, 2006). The extract of *Terminalia arjuna* Roxb showed better inhibition area against Gram -ve bacteria than Gram +ve bacteria (Mandal *et al.*, 2013).

Acacia ampliceps is also known as a salt wattle. It is a shrub or tree from the genus *Acacia*. It is a bushy shrub or tree that ranges from 1.5 to 9 meters in height (WWW, 2019). The living duration of *Acacia ampliceps* is from less than 10 upto 50 years (Anonymous, 2001). *Acacia ampliceps* has a shallow root organization and tolerate enormously saline and alkaline soils. Adaptable trials of this species out of the country have revealed that it can grow well from direct seeding. The wood has an air dry density of 660 kg/m³ and burns well providing good heat and leaving fine grey ash (Anonymous, 2001).

MATERIALS & METHODS

Plant collection

The parts of *Acacia ampliceps*, used in the present study, were obtained from Pakistan Forest Institute, Peshawar. The plant was identified and was given a check number and placed in the University Herbarium. The parts were then dried in the shade and the complete laboratory work was performed at the Department of Botany, Islamia University Peshawar.

Extraction

Acacia ampliceps aerial parts were broken into small pieces and then grinded and the powder was prepared. About 600 gm of plant material was soaked in methanol for about fourteen days. Filtration was done and the material was then placed at 60°C on rotary vacuum evaporator. The extract was further dried on a water bath at 55°C (Uddin *et al.*, 2011).

Fractionation

About seven grams of crude extracts were taken in 3 round flasks containing 300 ml each of ethyl acetate, ethanol and chloroform. After 24 hrs, the extract was filtered and concentrated through a rotary vacuum

December 31, 2019

evaporator at 60°C. The solvents were recollected and the concentrated fractions were dried at 55°C using a water bath and kept in vials (Uddin *et al.*, 2011).

Phytochemical Analysis

Qualitative phytochemical analysis of the extract of aerial parts of *Acacia ampliceps* was carried out according to (Oguyemi and Sofowora, 1979, Trease and Evans, 1989).

Alkaloids

About 10ml of methanol was put in a test tube, in which 0.1g of the extract was dissolved. A drop from it was put on filter paper and another drop from Dragendroff's reagent was put on the first drop. The filter paper became dried and was then washed with water. The appearance of orange color on the filter paper indicated the existence of alkaloids (Oguyemi and Sofowora, 1979).

Tannins

About 0.2g of the extract was assorted with H₂O and then heated. FeCl₃ was added to the mixture that gave it a dark green color which specified the occurrence of tannins (Trease and Evans, 1989).

Anthraquinones

About 5 mg of extract was heated along with 10% HCL in a water bath. Later than boiling, the filtrate was kept to cool and then chloroform was added along with 10% ammonia and heated. The Light pink color appeared that shows the existence of anthraquinones in the extract (Trease and Evans, 1989).

Glycosides

The plant extract was hydrolyzed with HCl. NaOH was then added to neutralize the extract. After that few drops of Fehling solution A, B was added. The occurrence of glycosides was indicated by the red color of the precipitate (Trease and Evans, 1989).

Reducing Sugars

The plant extract was shaken with distilled H₂O and filtered. Little amount of (Fehling solution A, B) was added. The solution was then boiled for a short time. The orange, red color of the precipitate confirmed reducing sugars in the sample (Trease and Evans, 1989).

Saponins

About 0.2g of plant extract was taken. Distilled water was added and then boiled. The frothing showed the activity of Saponins (Trease and Evans, 1989).

Flavonoids

About 0.2g of the plant extract was mixed with diluted base NaOH. HCl was then added to it. The mixture loses its color that indicates flavonoids in the sample (Trease and Evans, 1989).

Phlobatannins

About 0.5g of plant extract was taken and then dissolved in distilled H₂O. It was filtered. About 2% of HCl was added to the filtrate and then boiled. The Red precipitate confirmed the existence of phlobatannins (Trease and Evans, 1989).

Steroids

0.5g of the extract was taken. It was mixed with 2 ml of acetic anhydride in combination with about 2 ml of H₂SO₄. Color of the solution changed violet to green or blue (in some samples) suggested that steroids are present (Trease and Evans, 1989).

Terpenoids

For terpenoids, about 2ml of chloroform was added to 0.2gm of the plant extract. Concentrated H₂SO₄ was carefully added until a layer is formed. The border was turned reddish brown in color, which indicated the presence of terpenoids in the extract (Trease and Evans, 1989).

Antibacterial Screening

The antibacterial activities of different strains were examined by the methodology of NCCLS, 1997).

Culture Media

The bacterial strains were obtained from the Agriculture University of Peshawar (AUP) and the cultures of bacterial strains were grown on agar and the bacterial strains were then sub-cultured repeatedly on agar medium and were kept at 4°C.

Media Preparation and Sterilization

Around 2.8g of phytoagar was taken and dissolved in 100 ml of distilled H₂O. Nutrient broth of about 20 ml/test tube was poured into test tubes and flasks. The flasks and test tubes were air tightened with Al (Aluminum) foil. The sample was sterilized in an autoclave at 121°C for about 15-20 minutes. The whole procedure was carried out in a complete sterile atmosphere using a laminar flow cabinet (LFC). After some time, media was solidified and sterilized petri dishes were used to culture bacteria.

Test organisms

In the current study, about 6 bacterial strains were used. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *E. coli*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Citrobacter*, *Xanthomonas* and *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Preparation of inoculums

Bacteria were streaked on media using a wire loop. It was left for incubation for one day. The culture was inoculated in test tubes using the nutrient broth. About 10ml of suspensions were taken from the nutrient broth, dissolved in 1ml of distilled H₂O. The turbidity was checked with McFarland Turbidity Standard (Baker and Thornsberg, 1983).

Disc Diffusion Susceptibility Method

The antimicrobial evaluation was done by disc diffusion method. About 20ml of sterile Muller Hilton Agar (MHA) was transferred into plates. On each plate, about 50ml of standardized bacterial cultures were spread using a sterile glass transmitter. Sterile discs (6 mm in dia), made from Whatman filter paper were positioned on media. Then plant extracts of two unlike concentrations (1 and 2 mg/disc) in six and 12 ml volumes were used on the disc. Ciprofloxacin antibiotic was used as positive control and ciprofloxacin was applied in a concentration of (6 ml/disc) on separate petri plates. Dimethyl Sulfonate was served as a negative control. These plates were placed in incubator and zone of inhibition was measured in mm for each paper disc.

RESULTS

Qualitative Tests for Phytochemicals

December 31, 2019

The qualitative tests for different phytochemicals of aerial parts extract of *Acacia ampliceps* were carried out. The phytochemical analysis confirmed the presence of alkaloids, tannins, reducing sugars, saponins, flavonoids, terpenoids, anthraquinones, Glycosides, Phlobatanins, as shown in Table 1. Glycosides and phlobatanins were not present.

Table: 1. Qualitative Tests of (Aerial Parts) extracts of *Acacia ampliceps* Maslin

S. No.	Tests	Results
1	Alkaloids	+
2	Tannins	+
3	Reducing sugars	+
4	Saponins	+
5	Flavonoids	+
6	Terpenoids	+
7	Anthraquinones	+
8	Glycosides	-
9	Phlobatanins	-

Antibacterial Activity

The antibacterial activity of aerial parts extracts of *Acacia ampliceps* in different solvents like ethyl acetate, methanol, ethanol, and chloroform gave different results against different bacteria. Two antibiotics Azithromycin and Ciprofloxacin, were used against the bacteria. The most successful plant extract was ethanol extract that gave maximum zone of inhibition, followed by ethyl acetate and methanol. The chloroform plant extract was not capable of controlling all species of bacteria. Ethanolic extract against *Xanthomonas* spp. showed inhibition zone of 26 mm, ethyl acetate extract aerial extract was 20 mm, methanolic extract was 21 mm and chloroform showed no activity against *Xanthomonas* bacterium. The ethanol, ethyl acetate and methanolic extract inhibition zone against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* were 22 mm each while the chloroform remained unsuccessful against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. In ethanol extract against *Citrobacter*, the inhibition zone was 21 mm and for ethyl acetate and methanol, it was 20 mm each. Chloroform had shown no zone of inhibition. The inhibition zone given by ethanol extract against *Escherichia coli* was 22 mm, methanol extract was 21 mm and ethyl acetate extract was 20 mm. Chloroform extract remained fruitless against *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus Subtilis* also remained opposing to chloroform extract while inhibition zone exposed by ethanol was 21 mm, by ethyl acetate was 20 mm and by methanol was 19 mm.

Antibacterial activities of fractions of aerial parts of *Acacia ampliceps* Maslin against *Xanthomonas*

Plant extracts were obtained in different solvents and were experienced against *Xanthomonas* spp. to examine antibacterial potential. The antibacterial activity of (ethanol, methanol, ethyl acetate and chloroform) extract samples from aerial parts of *Acacia ampliceps* against *Xanthomonas* (Gram -ve) as shown in figure 1. The ethanolic extract showed about 17 mm of inhibition zone (ZI) in conc. of (1 mg/disc) and about 26 mm ZI in concentration of (2 mg/disc). Ethyl acetate extract showed about 19 mm inhibition zone (ZI) in conc. of (1 mg/disc) and 20 mm ZI in concentration of (2 mg/disc) correspondingly. The methanolic extract exhibited 16 mm ZI in conc. of (1 mg/disc) and 21 mm ZI in concentration of (2 mg/disc). Chloroform extract showed no activity.

December 31, 2019

Figure: 1. Antibacterial activities of fractions of aerial parts of *Acacia ampliceps* Maslin against *Xanthomonas*

Figure: 2. Antibacterial activities of fractions of aerial parts of *Acacia ampliceps* Maslin against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*

Antibacterial activities of different extracts samples from aerial parts of *Acacia ampliceps* against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*

The antibacterial activity of ethanolic, methanolic, ethyl acetate and chloroform aerial parts extracts from *Acacia ampliceps* Maslin against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (Gram –ve) as seen in figure 2. The ethyl acetate and methanolic extracts showed 20 mm each inhibition zone (ZI) in conc. of (1 mg/disc) and 22 mm zone of inhibition in conc. of (2 mg/disc). Ethanolic extracts showed 16 mm ZI in the concentration of (1mg/disc) and 22 mm ZI in the concentration of (2 mg/disc). The chloroform sample showed no zone of inhibition.

December 31, 2019

Figure: 3. Antibacterial activities of various solvent extracted samples from aerial parts of *Acacia ampliceps* against *Citrobacter*

Antibacterial activities of different extracts samples from aerial parts of *Acacia ampliceps* against *Citrobacter*

Ethanol extract showed an excellent zone of inhibition (ZI) against *Citrobacter* whereas ethyl acetate and methanolic also showed very good affect. The antibacterial activity of ethanolic, methanolic, ethyl acetate and chloroform extracts samples from aerial parts of *Acacia ampliceps* against *Citrobacter* (Gram -ve) as shown in figure 3. The ethanolic extract showed an 18 mm Inhibition zone in the concentration of (1 mg per disc) and 21 mm ZI in the concentration of (2 mg per disc). The ethyl acetate plant extract showed 18 mm ZI in the concentration of (1 mg/disc) and 20 mm ZI in concentration (2 mg/disc) (in that order. The methanolic extract showed 17 mm ZI in concentration (1 mg/disc) and 20 mm ZI in concentration (2 mg/disc). Chloroform extract sample has no inhibition in both the concentrations.

Antibacterial activities of different solvent extracted samples from aerial parts of *Acacia ampliceps* against *Escherichia coli*

All four extracts except Chloroform showed a very good effect against *E. coli*. The antibacterial potential of ethanolic, methanolic, ethyl acetate and chloroform extracts from *Acacia ampliceps* aerial parts against *E.coli* (Gram -ve) are shown in figure 4. The ethanolic extract exhibited 16 mm zone of inhibition in concentration of (1 mg/disc) and 22 mm in concentration (2 mg/disc). The methanolic extract showed a 19 mm inhibition zone in the concentration of (1 mg/disc) and a 21 mm inhibition zone in the concentration of (2 mg/disc). The ethyl acetate extracts showed 18 mm ZI in the concentration of (1 mg/disc) and 20 mm ZI in the concentration of (2 mg/disc).

Figure: 4. Antibacterial activities of various solvent extracted samples from Aerial parts of *Acacia ampliceps* against *Escherichia coli*

Antibacterial activities of different solvent extracted samples from Aerial parts of *Acacia ampliceps* against *Bacillus subtilis*

Ethanol and ethyl acetate showed good inhibition zone as compared to methanolic extract samples. The antibacterial potential of ethanolic, methanolic, ethyl acetate and chloroform extracted samples from aerial parts of *Acacia ampliceps* against *Bacillus subtilis* (Gram -ve) as shown in figure 5. The ethanolic extract sample exhibited 17 mm ZI in the concentration of (1 mg/disc) and 21 mm ZI in the concentration of (2 mg/disc) (respective. The ethyl acetate extract showed 20 mm each Zone of inhibition in concentration in the concentration of (1 and 2 mg/disc). Methanolic extract sample showed 15 mm ZI in the concentration of (1 mg/disc) and 19 mm ZI in the concentration of (2 mg/disc) Chloroform again showed no zone of inhibition.

Figure: 5. Antibacterial activities of various solvent extracted samples from Aerial parts of *Acacia ampliceps* against *Bacillus subtilis*

DISCUSSION

December 31, 2019

Secondary metabolites are obtained from plants that are not toxic and are more able to eradicate the growth of pathogens. These compounds have a significant remedial role against all human pathogens. The antimicrobial drugs have a high price, none accessibility at the exact place and exact time, besides these the bacterial resistance is varying problem. Keeping in inspection these troubles connected with antibacterial drugs the look for new, proficient, harmless, a smaller amount of toxic natural products is an immense confront for investigators. To deal with this difficulty, the present work was designed to discover the antibacterial activities of *Acacia ampliceps* plant with the expectation of discovering efficient, harmless and low-priced antibacterial medicine.

In the current study, the phytochemicals that are found in aerial parts of *Acacia ampliceps* were alkaloids, tannins, reducing sugars, saponins, flavonoids and terpenoids (Table 1). In the stem bark of *Acacia ferruginea* saponins, flavonoids, tannins, and carbohydrates have been reported (Deb and Dash, 2014). Also, in the bark of *Acacia nilotica* alkaloids, saponins, flavonoids, tannins were present (Deshpande *et al.* 2012). In the heartwood of *Acacia catechu* catechins, tannins and flavonoids are also reported (Rajendra *et al.* 2011). Phytochemical testing discovered the presence of saponins, glycosides, tannins and flavonoids in the leaves of *Acacia sieberiana* (Oladipo *et al.*, 2012).

The methanol extracts of pods of *Acacia nilotica* L. and bark of *Acacia catechu* were reported to be the most effective against 4 bacteria (*S. aureus*, *E.coli* and *S. typhii*) *A. nilotica* and *A. catechu* were found to have different main secondary metabolites (Saini *et al.*, 2002). This indicate that species of genus *Acacia* are relatively high in biologically active secondary metabolites and these metabolites are found in *Acacia* are significant for a diversity of functions, principal amongst these are diuretic (glucosides), indigestion problems (saponins, tannins and flavonoids), antioxidant (phenols), anti-cancer (terpenoids and also saponins), anti-plasmodial (amines, tannins, organic acids and saponins), vital nutraceutical (polysaccharide and gums) and natriuretic (glucosides) (Saini *et al.*, 2002). The *E.coli* was inhibited by the three extracts like ethyl acetate, ethanol and methanol extracts while chloroform extract remained fruitless. The ethyl acetate, ethanol and methanol are the most excellent solvents for extraction. Chloroform extracts a smaller amount of constituents, so it was not active against the 5 tested Bacteria (Levine, 1987). The *Acacia ampliceps* exposed the existence of flavonoids, which may be dynamic against *E. coli*. (Arias *et al.*, 2004). *Acacia tortillis* Forsk. extracts of leaves, stem bark and roots showed antibacterial activity in resistance to *E. coli*, *P.aeruginosa*, *S. aureus*, *Streptococcus pyogene*, *Shigella sp.*, and *S. typhii* also diverse secondary metabolites such as saponins, tannins, volatile oil, alkaloid and phenol were found in the plant (Kubmarowa *et al.*, 2012). *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* growth was inhibited by ethanolic, ethyl acetate and methanolic extracts. The chloroform extract showed no action against *Pseudomonas*. The antimicrobial ability of 7 ethanolic extracts and 3 aqueous extracts from *Acacia aroma* Gill were studied against 163 multi-resistant bacterial strains. All the ethanolic extracts were good against gram (+ve) bacteria. The majority active against gram(-ve) bacteria (*E. coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*) were extracts of flowers and leaves. *Acacia aroma* Gill. Leaves extracts showed a high level of flavonoid substance. The leaf extracts may have revealed antibacterial resistance in connection with those of flavonoids, both for Gram (+ve) and Gram (-ve) bacteria. The extracts of flower showed antibacterial resistance against Gram (+ve) bacteria in association with terpenes and flavonoids (Arias *et al.*, 2004). *Acacia senegal* L. stem bark extracts showed antibacterial affect against *Proteus vulgaris*, *E.coli*, *P.aeruginosa*, *Shigella dysenteriae*, *S. thyphi* and *K. pneumonia*. Thus, the present research work obviously reveals the antibacterial potential of *Acacia ampliceps* Maslin.

CONCLUSION

The present study was designed to explore the phytochemical and antimicrobial potential of ethyl acetate, ethanol, chloroform and methanol extracts of *Acacia ampliceps* Maslin. The extract samples were used against *Bacillus subtilis*, *Xanthomonas*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli* and *Citrobacter*. Phytochemical results showed that major classes of natural products detected were alkaloids, tannins, reducing sugars, Saponins, flavonoids, terpenoids and anthraquinones. Ethanol extracted sample against *Xanthomonas* (173 %)

showed the maximum zone of inhibition which was the best one, followed by Ethyl acetate extract against *Xanthomonas* (158 %). The lowest zone of inhibition was measured for chloroform extracted samples against all bacterial strains (0 %). *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was most resistant but *Xanthomonas* specie was most vulnerable. These results show that aerial parts of *Acacia ampliceps* Maslin have a potentially broad spectrum antibacterial activity. The existence of diverse phytochemicals in the plant is the promising answer for its active antimicrobial profile. In the future, efforts will be made to isolate bioactive constituents of *Acacia ampliceps* Maslin extract to find possible pharmacological agents.

REFERENCES

- i. Ahmad, I., A.Z. Beg. 2001. Antimicrobial and phytochemical studies on 45 Indian medicinal plants against multiple drug resistant human pathogens. *J. Ethanopharma*. 74, pp. 113-123.
- ii. Ali, M.S., M. Jahangir. 2001. Thanks God for the gift the medicine. *Hamdard Medica XLIV4*: pp.114-124.
- iii. Anonymous. 2001. *Flora of Australia*. 11A, pp. 673.
- iv. Arias, M.E., J.D. Gomez, N.M. Cudmani. 2004. Ethanolic and aqueous extracts of *Acacia aroma*. *Life sciences*. pp. 75: 191-202.
- v. Baker, C.N. and C.N. Thornsberg. 1983. Inoculum standardization in antimicrobial susceptibility tests: evaluation overnight age cultures. *Journal of Clinical Microbiology*. 17, pp. 140-157.
- vi. Cowan, M.M. 1999. Plant products as antimicrobial agents. *Clin. Microbial*. 12, pp. 564-582.
- vii. De Smith. 1997. The role of plant-derived drugs and herbal medicines in Healthcare Drugs.54, pp. 801-840.
- viii. Deb N.K, Dash G.K. 2014. Pharmacognostical studies of *Gardenia latifolia* Ait. Barks. *Der Pharmacia Lettre*. 6(4):267-271.
- ix. Deshpande, S.N. and D.G. Kadam. 2013. Phytochemical and antibacterial activity of *Acacia nilotica* L. against *streptococcus mutans*. *Int. J pharm sci*. vol. (5), pp. 236-238.
- x. Doughari, J.H. 2006. Antimicrobial Activity of *Tamarindusindica* Linn. *Trop J Pharm Res* 5(2), pp. 597-603.
- xi. Edeoga, H.O., D.E. Okwu and B.O. Mbaebie. 2005. Phytochemical constituents of some Nigerian medicinal plants. *African Journal of Biotechnology*. 4(7), pp. 685-688.
- xii. Efferth, T., Y.J. Fu, G. Shwarz, V.S. Konkimall, M. Wink. 2007. Molecular target-guided Tumor therapy with natural products derived from traditional Chinese Medicine. *Curr.Med Chem*.14, pp. 2024-2032.
- xiii. Gill, M.A. 2003. Cultivation of medicinal and aromatic herbs: Experience of IMHSC, Editors: Hasan A, Khan MA and Ahmad M. Conservation and Sustainable uses of medicinal and aromatic plants of Pakistan.
- xiv. Heber. 2004. PDR for herbal medicine, 3rd edition, Thomson publication.5, pp. 42-43
- xv. Kim, H., S.W. Park, J.M. Park, K.H. Moon, C.K. Lee. 1995. Screening and isolation of antibiotic resistance inhibitors from herb material Resistant Inhibition of 21 Korean plants. *Nat. Prod. Sci*. 1, pp. 50-54.
- xvi. Kubmarowa, D., M.E. Khan and A. Shuaibu. 2012. Comparative phytochemical screening and biological evaluation of n-hexane and water extracts of *Acacia tortilis*. *Research in pharmaceutical biotechnology*. 4(2), pp. 18-23.
- xvii. Levine, M.M. 1987. *Escherichia coli* that cause diarrhea: Enterotoxigenic, Enteropathogenic, Enteroinvasive, Enterohemorrhagic and Enteroadherent. *The J. of infectious diseases*. vol. 155, No.3.
- xviii. Liu, L., D.G. Durham, R.M.E. Richards. 2011. Vancomycin resistance reversal in enterococci by flavonoids, *J. of Pharm pharmacol*.53, pp. 129-32.
- xix. Mandal, S., A. Petra, A. Samanta, S. Roy, A. Mandal, T.D. Mahapatra, S. Pradhan, K. Das, D.K. Nandi. 2013. Analysis of Phytochemical profile of *Terminalia arjuna* Roxb. Bark extract with antioxidative and antimicrobial properties. *Asian Pc J Trop Biomed*. 3(12), pp. 960-966.
- xx. Nasir, R., S. Chanda. 2006. Activity of some medicinal plants against certain bacterial pathogenic strains, Phytochemical, Saurashtra University, Rajkot-360005, Gujrat, Indian.

December 31, 2019

- xxi. National Committee for Clinical Laboratory Standards. Performance standards for antimicrobial disk susceptibility tests. Approved standard M2-A6. Wayne, Pa: National Committee for Clinical Laboratory Standards; 1997
- xxii. Oguyemi, A.Q. and Sofowora, A. 1979. Proceedings of a Conference on African Medicinal Plants. Ife-Ife: Univ Ife. pp. 20-22
- xxiii. Oumzil, H., S. Ghoulemi, M. Rhajaoui, A. Ildrissi, S. Fkih-Tetouani, M. Faid, A. Benjouad. 2002. Antibacterial and antifungal activity of essential oils of *Mentha suaveolens*, *Phytother Res.* 16, pp. 727-31.
- xxiv. Pa, R., L. Mathew. 2012. Antimicrobial activity of leaf extracts of *Justicia adhatoda* L. in comparison with vasicine. *Asian Pacific J of Tropical Biomedicine.* pp. 1556-1560.
- xxv. Pavithra, P.S., V.S. Janani, K.H. Charumathi, R. Indumathy, S. Potala, R.S. Verma. 2010. Antibacterial activity of the plant used in Indian herbal medicine. *Int. J. of green pharma.* 10, pp. 22-28.
- xxvi. Preethi, R., V.V. Devanathan, M. Loganathan. 2010. Antimicrobial and Antioxidant Efficacy of Some Medicinal Plants against Food Borne Pathogens. *Adv. in Bio. Res.* 4 (2), pp. 122-125.
- xxvii. Rajendra, P., D. Titiksh, P. Rasika, G. Vandana and R. Nikhil. 2011. Antiulcer activity of *Acacia catechu* Wild in rats. 2(5), pp. 1585-1587.
- xxviii. Rauf, A., N. Muhammad, A. Khan, N. Uddin, M. Atif and Barkatullah. 2012. Antibacterial and Phytotoxic Profile of Selected Pakistani Medicinal Plants, *Journal of World Applied Sciences.* 20(4), pp. 540-544.
- xxix. Saini, M.L., R. Saini, S. Roy, and A. Kumar. 2002. Comparative pharmacognostical and antimicrobial studies of *Acacia* species. *J. of Medicinal plants Research.* 2(12), pp. 378-386.
- xxx. Sanjay, J., S. Satyaendra, Satish, S. Sumbhate. 2007. Recent trends in *Curcuma Longa* Linn. *Phcogmag.* 1, pp. 119-128.
- xxxi. Saupe, S.G. 2005. Screening for Biodynamic plants, *Plants and Human Affairs.* Biology Department. College of St. Benedict/St. John's University, Collegeville.
- xxxii. Sen, A. and A. Batra. 2012. Evaluation of Antimicrobial Activity of Different Solvent Extracts of Medicinal Plant *Melia azedarach* L. *int. J. current pharma. Res.* 4.
- xxxiii. Shah, N.Z., A.K. Mir, N. Muhammad and, S. Azeem. 2012. Antimicrobial and Phytotoxic Study of *Conyza canadensis*. *Middle-East Journal of Medicinal Plants Research.* 1(3), pp. 63-67.
- xxxiv. Shah, N.Z., N. Muhammad, S. Azeem and A. Rauf. 2012. Studies on the Chemical constituents and Antioxidant profile of *Conyza canadensis*, *Middle-East Journal of Medicinal Plants Research.* 1 (2), pp. 32-35
- xxxv. Shah, N.Z., N. Muhammad, A.Z. Khan, M. Samie, H. Khan, S. Azeem, G. Uddin and A. Rauf. 2013. Phytochemical Analysis and Antioxidant Studies of *Conyza bonariensis*. *Academic J. of plant sci.* 6(3), pp. 109-112.
- xxxvi. Sharma, A. 2011. Antibacterial activity of ethanolic extracts of some arid zone plants. *Int. J. of Pharm.Tech.* 3(1), pp. 283-286.
- xxxvii. Shinwari, Z.K., I. Khan, S. Nazand, A. Hussain. 2009. Assessment of antibacterial activity of three plants used in Pakistan to cure respiratory disease, *African Journal of Biotechnology.* 8(24), pp. 7082-7086.
- xxxviii. Shinwari, Z.K., T. Watanabe, M. Rehman, T.A. Yoshikawa. 2006. Pictorial Guide to Medicinal Plants of Pakistan. KUST. Kohat, Pakistan.
- xxxix. Srinivasan, K., D. Natarajan, M.A.N. Dheen, G. Perumal, C. Mohanasundari, K. Prabakar, R. Sengottuvel. 2006. Antibacterial activity of selected medicinal plants. *Hamdard Medics XLIX.* 2, pp. 5-8.
- xl. Trease, G.E. and W.C. Evans. 1989. *Pharmacognosy* (13th edition). English Language Books Society, Bailliere Tindall, Britain. Pp. 378, 386-480.
- xli. Uddin, G., A. Rauf, B.S. Siddiqui and S.Q. Shah. 2011. Preliminary Comparative phytochemical Screening of *Diospyros Lotus* Stewart, *Middle-East Journal Scientific Research.* 10(1), pp. 78-81.

December 31, 2019

- xlii. Uddin, G., A. Rauf, N. Muhammad, Shabana, N. Malik and Mohsina. 2012. *Phytochemical and Pharmacological Studies of the Whole Plant of Calotropis Procera*, Middle- East Journal of Medicinal Plants Research. 1(4), pp. 71-74.
- xliii. Uddin, G., A. Rauf, T.U. Rehman and M. Qaisar. 2011. *Phytochemical Screening of Pistacia chinensis var. integerrima*, Middle-East Journal Scientific Research. 7(5), pp. 707-711.
- xliv. Uddin, G., M. Alam, B.S. Siddiqui, A. Rauf, N. Uddin and N. Muhammad. 2013. *Preliminary Phytochemical Profile and Antibacterial Evaluation of Viburnum grandiflorum Wall*, Global, J. of pharmacology. 7(2), pp. 133-137.
- xlv. Uddin, G., W. Ullah, A. Rauf, B.S. Siddiqui, A. Ahmad, C. Bibi, M. Qaisar and S. Azam. 2011. *Phytochemical Screening and Antimicrobial Activity of Cornus macrophylla wall. Ex Roxb*, Middle_East Journal of Scientific Research. 9(4), pp. 516-519.
- xlvi. World Wide Wattle. "Acacia ampliceps Salt Wattle". CSIRO publishing. Retrieved 24 March 2019.
- xlvii. Zgoda, J.R., J.R. Porter. 2001. *A convenient micro dilution method screening natural products against bacteria and fungi*. Pharm. Biol. 39, pp. 221-225.